

MISCELLANEA

The forest area of Nepal

We are indebted to H.B. Pradhan for a detailed note headed: 'What is the forest coverage in Nepal? Is it 29 percent or 42.7 percent?'. On looking into this subject, we find that it is discussed, in generally similar terms, by R.S. Nield, in his 'Working paper for the seminar on fuelwood and fodder - problems and policy. Appendix I - What is the forest area of Nepal?' (1985). Interested readers will find related background material, referring to India, in the paper by Ashbindu Singh that is noticed in our Abstract 2/87 in this issue.

The figure of 29 % (or 29.1 %, but we doubt if the third significant figure is justified) comes from a 'Reconnaissance inventory of the major ecological land units and their watershed condition in Nepal', published by the Department of Soil and Watershed Management and FAO in 1980. It seems to have been widely accepted as the best estimate of the remaining forest coverage of the country.

The 42.7 % is quoted by Pradhan from a table produced by the Land Resource Mapping Project (LRMP) in 1985. Nield uses mainly another LRMP figure of 38.1 %. Both agree that it is a question of definitions, and Nield makes the point that the two sources are in surprisingly close agreement if one selects from them the most directly comparable estimates. The 'FAO' figure of 29.1 % applies to forested land with more than 50 % crown cover; the LRMP gives 28.1 % for land with more than 40 % crown cover.

As well as this 28.1 %, the LRMP gives another 10 % with 10-40 % tree cover, and 4.7 % with shrubs, so it could be said that there is some kind of forest on 42.8 % (Pradhan: 42.7). However, there is also 11.9 % of 'grassland' and 6.7 % of 'noncultivated inclusion' (uncultivated areas too small to map separately), not to mention 'other' (rock, ice, etc.).

Apart from definitions, there is another major difference between the FAO and the LRMP figures. It is very briefly summarized by Nield as: 'the FAO study was at a reconnaissance level, using visual interpretation of unenhanced satellite imagery at scales

of from 1:250,000 to 1:500,000, with fairly limited field checking. The LRMP study was much more detailed using 1:50,000 stereo air photographs combined with much more fieldwork'. In terms of remote-sensing theory, it is very interesting that satellite imagery can give a reasonably accurate broad-brush picture, but for fuller details one has to turn to aerial photography - or at least this was so when these two studies were made.

The popularity of the '29 %' figure is perhaps unfortunate, and it might be better to think of the forested area as 'about 40 %', but clearly the bare figures, detached from their definitions, and without reference to their derivation, have little significance. It is also clear that any serious discussion of land-use statistics in Nepal should be based on the detailed and accurate studies made by the LRMP, which are now available in a series of printed volumes.

Keyword: Statistics.

Sandalwood in Nepal

This note, on the interesting question of whether it might be possible to cultivate sandalwood in Nepal, has been supplied by P.M. Amatya of the Royal Botanical Garden and Royal Palace Garden, Kathmandu.

Sandalwood, Santalum album L., of the family Santalaceae, would be a valuable tree to introduce to Nepal. It is important not only in religion (during worship small pieces of the wood are burned) but also in medicine, perfumery, and wood carving.

It is found in southern India, especially in Karnataka, Kerala and Tamil Nadu, and also in Sri Lanka, Burma, Malaysia, Australia, and Hawaii. It is probably not native to India, but introduced there many centuries ago.

It is a root parasite, its hosts including grasses and bamboos as well as many tree species (see for example Troup, The silviculture of Indian trees, vol. III, 1921).

So far as is known, no attempts had been made to introduce it to Nepal until the writer was sent eight seeds

in 1983, from Mr E.T. Ekanayake, Director of the Peradenia Botanic Garden, Sri Lanka. Four of these seeds germinated and were grown on as seedlings in the greenhouse at the Royal Botanical Gardens, Godavari. Then, while visiting Peradenia in November 1983 the writer was able to collect about 250 g of seed. Advice on germination techniques was obtained from Dr Purohit of the Multichem Research Centre, Nandesware, Baroda. In January 1984 various pre-sowing treatments were tried, viz. soaking in concentrated sulphuric acid diluted with 1, 2 and 3 parts of water for 4, 6, 12 and 24 hours; soaking in warm water; and (control) untreated. All the seeds treated with acid diluted with only one or two parts of water died. The other treatments gave the following results:

Seeds germinated out of 50 sown

Seed lot	Sulphuric acid 1:3				Warm water	Control
	4h	6h	12h	24h		
1	25	40	12	8	15	10
2	26	43	14	10	17	11

In the control treatment germination took three months; in the acid treatments it took 27-40 days. A few plants were attacked by a damping-off disease. The seedlings were transplanted into a 1:1:1 mixture of soil, sand and compost in April-May, at the four-leaf stage. Fertilizer was given at fortnightly intervals. Plants were distributed to various places in or near Hetauda and Kathmandu. At the time of writing there are three surviving plants at Brindaban Herbal Farm and another three at Kanti Iswari bungalow, both near Hetauda. All six are established with an Albizia sp. as host. Other plants, with no hosts, have died. A few more are still growing in their pots.

It seems that it might be possible to grow sandalwood commercially at low altitude sites in Nepal. The recommended nursery procedures are to soak the seeds in 1:3 sulphuric acid for 6 hours and sow them in a mixture of 3 parts sand and 1 part sawdust. For winter sowing, bottom heat is recommended (using solar heating). The seed box should be covered with polythene sheet to increase the humidity, but the temperature should not be allowed to go above 25°C.

Keywords: Santalum album.

Gummosis in Leucaena

World Neighbors, who have been promoting Leucaena leucocephala in Nepal, have become slightly concerned about the occurrence of a gummosis disorder. So far it has been observed only on a small number of trees in the Sindhu-palanchowk District, and is probably not a major problem in Nepal, but any further observations should be reported. Gummosis of Leucaena is well known in India.

The Division of Plant Pathology of the Department of Agriculture has identified the causal organism as Fusarium semitectum, which has been recorded on more than fifty other hosts in Nepal. Professor Brewbaker of the University of Hawaii at Manoa has provided some general observations on gummosis. He suggests that genetic resistance to the disease is probably very variable, and that it is likely to be aggravated by phosphorus deficiency, water-logging, or damage to the plants at the time of planting.

A note by Hata Ram Baidya of World Neighbors says that the symptoms are oozing gum, dark bands on the bark, vertical cracks and sometimes swelling of the bark. The roots of diseased seedlings are dark brown. Leaflets have black or very dark brown spots and may also carry a heavy white fungal growth. Seedpods may be deformed, and the seeds may have black or dark brown patches.

Although the disease spreads in various ways, and will probably come into contact with the host sooner or later, only a very small proportion of the host plants develop disease symptoms. Infection through seed is controlled by the normal pre-sowing treatment in boiling water.

Keywords: Leucaena leucocephala; Fusarium semitectum; diseases of trees.

IUFRO Working Party S.07-09

The subject of IUFRO Working Party S.07-09 is 'Silviculture of Plantation Forests in Latin America'. Ian Napier, the Technical Cooperation Officer specializing in nursery research with the Nepal-UK Forestry Research Project, has received a copy of the Working Party's Newsletter No. 12, which contains the news that it has been decided to form similar

working parties for Africa and Asia. All three will come under the IUFRO Subject Group S1.07, Tropical Silviculture.

The Newsletter also contains the titles of the 41 papers presented at a Symposium on the theme 'Techniques for producing fuelwood on small farms', held at the CATIE campus in Turrialba, Costa Rica [date not given]

Another item of potential interest to Nepal foresters is a list compiled in answer to a questionnaire to members of the Working Party, comprising titles of recent publications in their field. We are not repeating this information here, since most of the publications date in fact from about 1984, and those of most interest are probably known already to our readers.

Keywords: IUFRO; publications; fuelwood; plantations.

Alley farming

A workshop on this kind of agroforestry was held in Ibadan, Nigeria, on 10-15 March, 1986. The Proceedings are available from Dr B.T. Kang, IITA, PMB 5320, Oyo Road, Ibadan, Nigeria. [ACIAR Forestry Newsletter No. 2, Sept./Oct. 1986, p. 4].

Keyword: agroforestry.

Working Group on Fodder Trees, Forest Fodder and Leaf Litter

The following note has been supplied by Dr P.J. Robinson, Fodder Tree Specialist in the Nepal-UK Forestry Research Project.

In June 1986 the FRP organized a working group on fodder tree/forest fodder and leaf litter research and development. Thirty-six participants from nineteen government departments and aid organizations attended the one-day meeting. The main reasons for forming the group are:

- Tree fodder is of crucial importance to livestock production, and to farm production generally, in Nepal. Tree foliage is also important for other purposes, such as making compost. Ground fodder is collected or grazed in large quantities: it is technically possible for forests to be managed so as to increase ground

fodder production. Fodder resources are shrinking, and cropland fertility is said to be decreasing, so it is highly desirable to increase the availability of foliage and forest fodder.

- Many projects are doing very interesting work, but this work is sometimes not known to other people; a sharing of experiences would be very valuable.

- Little research has been done, and there are often no standard research methodologies. It is very desirable to discuss techniques which would give comparable results between different projects. Several projects are starting research, so these discussions should be held soon.

- A lot of research is needed, but few projects have much in the way of resources or expertise, so it is particularly desirable to avoid unnecessary duplication.

- It is essential to bring together specialists in different disciplines.

The Chief Conservator of Forests, Mr M. Haque, opened the meeting. In his address, he recommended that the group should help to find out what research and development work is being done, and where; what work needs to be done; and who is going to undertake specific aspects of it.

Sixteen people briefly described their past, present and likely future activities. These presentations are to be published in an FRP Occasional Paper. Three sub-groups were formed, each including different disciplines, to discuss priorities. Their conclusions will also be included in the Occasional Paper. Important topics were listed under the headings of Technical, Operational and Socio-economic research, and Extension. Technical topics were grouped as tree-specific, animal-specific, and tree/crop interactions.

There were also discussions on village surveys to ascertain fodder tree preferences in different parts of Nepal. Two detailed proposed questionnaires were circulated by FRP and UMN (United Mission to Nepal). Several organizations were interested in trying out these questionnaires, or modified versions of them, and would discuss their experiences at the next meeting. (As far as is known, some trials have since been made by the Winrock

Agricultural Research Project, UMN, Pakhribas Agricultural Centre, and FRP. It was also agreed that a short, simple questionnaire should be prepared which could be used by people without experience of interviewing; if completed in many parts of the country by different projects it would give useful information on species distribution and abundance, and on the farmers' preferences and their demand for different species. To get comparable results it is essential that the questions should be asked in the same way. The English and Nepali versions of this questionnaire are reproduced at the end of this issue of Banko Janakari. Further details will be given in the FRIC Occasional Paper.

It is to be hoped that as many organizations as possible will engage on this collaborative effort. The results will be entered on a database at the FRP, analysed, and made generally available. Anyone interested should contact:

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Keywords: fodder; grazing; litter.

Forestry Research Compendium

The Forestry Research Project is preparing a compendium of forestry research in Nepal. The aim is to trace and record as much as possible of the research in progress or completed at the end of 1986. More than six hundred studies have been recorded so far, covering the period 1965-1986. Records are being stored in a computerized database which can be analysed to find out what has been done on a particular topic, or species, or site. The database makes it quick and simple to find out, for example, what research has been done on the growth of Pinus patula above 2000 m in the Western Region. The records are brief and do not usually give the results of the research, but they do indicate if and where results are available. Anyone working in forestry in Nepal will be able to request a search of the records by writing to FRIC or calling in at the office in Kathmandu. It is planned to print the compendium as it stands and to publish this 'paper' version in April 1987. The computer record will be maintained and amended

if any other records are unearthed. Future printed versions, however, will concentrate on new research or research that was already recorded but still continuing at the end of 1986.

Keyword: research.

Updated Directory

In 1982 a directory was published as a supplement to the Nepal Forestry Technical Information Bulletin, listing all organizations and institutions in Nepal that were known to have an interest in forestry. This proved to be a popular and much used reference list. It has now been brought up to date by Jane Carter on behalf of the Forestry Research Project. The new version, compiled from questionnaires completed in respect of sixty-five organizations (including government departments as well as aid agencies, commercial firms, etc.), is being issued to all the organizations listed. Anyone else who wishes to receive a copy should apply to FRIC. The directory is now computerized and will be brought up-to-date whenever new information is received; it is hoped to make and issue a complete revision again in about two years' time.

Bhutan

Unasyva (1986, Vol. 38 No. 1, pp. 46-51) contains a report of an interview, by Jenny Devitt, with Chenkap Dorji, former Director of Forests, Royal Government of Bhutan, of some interest to foresters working in Nepal. One of the main points is that 'conservation' is emphasized, as opposed to exploitation for revenue. The present policy is said to be based partly on observations of 'the depleted forest resources of the kingdom's neighbours and those of other Asian countries.' The relatively low population density (about 22 people per square kilometre) has helped, and in a few places where the population is more concentrated there has been some local excessive deforestation. A short account is given of the Gedu plywood factory, so far the only wood-based industry. No details are given of yield regulation in the forests that supply logs to this factory, apart from the comment that dead and dying trees are used first and then the older trees 'in order to let the younger ones underneath grow more strongly.'

A fresh look at bamboos

Alison Blake, of Voluntary Service Overseas, has been assisting Chris Stapleton with his continuing studies on bamboos in Nepal. This note is based on her reports of two field trips, to parts of Ilam and Taplejung Districts, both in east Nepal, at about 1350 and 1800 m respectively. In Ilam, help was provided by Krisna Man Singh, a Ranger with the Community Forestry Development Project, who took part in interviews with farmers.

It is worth summarizing the main results of these enquiries, even if some of the information is already known from other sources.

Importance of bamboos

For all the farmers interviewed, bamboos were an important crop, even on very small holdings. They are essential for house construction, as well as for animal outhouses and pens. They are also needed for various tools, utensils, etc. They provide animal fodder and some human food, as well as fuel. In some cases they are a source of cash income.

Main species

In Ilam it was noted that the usual pattern of bamboo cultivation was to have a majority of mal bans (Bambusa nutans), one or two clumps of choya bans (Dendrocalamus hamiltonii) and bhalu bans (D. hookeri) and occasionally ban bans (another variety of D. hamiltonii) - which is also found occurring naturally in the forest. Nigalo (Drepanostachyum sp.) was confined to the higher altitudes.

Mal bans is also the preferred species in Taplejung. The 'choya bans' in Taplejung, although it has been identified from its flowers as the same species as in Ilam, seems to be a notably different variety; the culms are smooth and glossy, resembling those of mal bans and of only slightly greater diameter (8-10 cm on good sites), the culm sheaths are smoothly tapering, lacking auricles and cilia, and with little pubescence. Bhalu bans is much the largest species in Taplejung (9-13 cm d.b.h.). One farmer there claimed to distinguish two varieties of it: one (kalo) with thicker walls and the other (rato) with thinner walls and reddish culms when mature. Padang (Drepanostachyum hookerianum) is grown in Taplejung

from cuttings brought down from higher altitudes. Malingo (Arundinaria spp.) is reported to be still common in the high altitude forests, and another weaving species, singane, identified as a Drepanostachyum sp., is cultivated at lower altitudes. It is about the same size as padang, with glossy, golden-coloured culms. One clump of dhanu bans (Bambusa balcooa) was also seen.

Flowering and natural regeneration

One farmer recounted that malingo had formerly been plentiful in the forest but had flowered seven years ago and had not successfully regenerated, presumably on account of grazing pressure. In the Change Panchayat of Taplejung District, many choya bans clumps had flowered in recent years. The clumps are said to die back 9-10 years after flowering; the clumps are then cut back, and vigorous new shoots come up. The local PAC forester had noted that in each flower cluster there were usually only one or two seeds.

Cultivation

Planting is always by the use of offset cuttings, 1-4 m high, with about 60-90 cm of rhizome attached. They are planted in March-April, and success is about 50-100%. Some efforts have been made by foresters to grow choya bans from seed.

Bamboos are not generally given manure (except what they get when the clumps are used as 'charpi'!) but a common practice is to throw old roof thatch into the clumps; this can induce good growth, e.g. of mal bans, even on poor shallow soils.

Growth

Some observations were made of the different sizes attained by mal bans on different sites. Whereas on good sites d.b.h. can be about 7-9 cm, it was only 4.5-6 on some very dry, steep and south-facing slopes at relatively high altitudes in Taplejung.

Use in construction

Bamboo lasts a long time within and inside the mud walls of the houses; up to a hundred years is suggested. However, exposed parts of the construction, such as porch supports, and also the animal shelters, which are unprotected, need frequent renewal,

perhaps every 3-6 years. One interesting remark from Taplejung was that thatching grass is becoming scarce, so that thatch is not renewed often enough, and the bamboo roof supports suffer, and have to be renewed oftener.

Mal bans is favoured for construction. Bhalu bans is used for large upright supports although it may only last two years in contact with the ground; it is also used for vegetable supports. In Taplejung its use for vegetable supports and fencing was explained by saying that mal bans was too valuable and choya bans too weak for such purposes. Choya bans is used for weaving, and for the ties which bind house poles together. In Taplejung, padang, malingo and singane are also used for weaving; one large house was seen at about 2850 m that was made entirely from woven bamboo mats.

Use as fodder

Bamboo fodder is used mainly in winter when other fodder is scarce, and few if any farmers depend on it exclusively to feed their animals all year round. Mal bans is the preferred fodder species; cows and buffaloes are said to give less milk if fed choya bans or bhalu bans. In Taplejung, padang is also a preferred fodder species, as well as nigalo when available.

Use as firewood

Generally only old, broken or diseased culms are used for firewood, unless there is a large surplus in winter; the cut tops left after leaves have been stripped for fodder are also burned. Choya bans is considered a poor fuelwood and bhalu bans a good one. Bamboo burns with a hot flame, but too quickly.

Use as food

Choya bans is the main source of edible shoots. They are only eaten by households that have a large surplus of this species.

Other uses

Bamboos have very many uses. Particular ones noted on these visits were:

choya bans for weaving ropes to tether livestock; bhalu bans for pots, including 'tumba' pots at Limbu weddings and funerals, but also for milking, and for household containers more generally.

Management

In Ilam: 'Questioned about management, farmers tended to indicate that there was none; bamboo it seems is very much regarded as something that can look after itself...culms are generally cut at three years or as needed.' It was noted, however, that a commercial grower's clumps were small, well thinned and healthy, with about twenty culms per clump. In Taplejung also, bamboos tended to be cut when needed, but in general only up to a fifth or a third of the culms in a clump are cut in one year, and 1-2 year old culms are not cut, except for choya bans, which may be cut at 2 years, when they are still flexible for weaving.

Economics

Both the areas visited appear to have an overall surplus of bamboos, but with the depletion of supplies of other woody material there are signs of a shortage developing. At a very rough estimate, each family uses some 40-50 culms per annum. Culms sell for 5-10 rupees each, so are a major expense for any farmer who does not have a sufficient supply of his own. It is common for people at higher altitudes to have to buy mal bans for house construction from people living lower down.

In Ilam there are commercial growers who cultivate land too steep or poor for other crops, and this is apparently a profitable occupation. In Taplejung, where there is no road access, there is no commercial market; small quantities are given away, and larger quantities sold at low prices.

Keywords; Arundinaria; Bambusa balcooa; Bambusa nutans; Dendrocalamus hamiltonii; Dendrocalamus hookeri; Drepanostachyum; Drepanostachyum hookerianum; bamboos.